

Impact Factor : 5.132

UGC Serial No. 42685

Registration No. 206

ISSN :- 2348-6228

CURRENT JOURNAL

Journal For All Research

An International Peer Reviewed Research Refereed Quarterly Journal

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Volume 10

No. -28

(April_June. 2022)

Published by
Vishal Bharat Sansthan
Varanasi (U.P.) India

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Open Network for Digital Commerce (ONDC): Unlocking Digital-led Growth

Shameem Ahmad

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Abstract:

Similar to how India accomplished with the UPI, the Open Network for Digital Commerce (ONDC) offers a singular opportunity for India to modernize its digital commerce environment and set an example for the rest of the globe. An opportunity like ONDC only comes along once in a decade, but it has enormous potential for a strong buyer and seller ecosystem. A general summary of the ONDC in India is provided in this report. To encourage innovation, competition, and consumer choice in the e-commerce industry, the government has launched the ONDC, which intends to provide an open, transparent, and interoperable network for digital commerce. It examines ONDC's main characteristics, difficulties, fundamental components, and other elements. The paper contributes to the ongoing debate on the role of open networks in promoting innovation, competition, and consumer welfare in the digital economy, particularly in emerging markets like India.

Keywords: ONDC, e-Commerce, Network, payment gateway, buyer and seller.

1. Introduction:

The Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade (DPIIT) of the Government of India formed the private, non-profit Section 8 Company known as the Open Network for Digital Commerce (ONDC) to promote open e-commerce in the nation. It was established on December 30, 2021, with limited liability and under the same high standards of corporate governance as listed corporations. Because private sector institutions hold the bulk of this business, the close market alignment, flexibility, and agility in decision-making, as well as the resources necessary for the success of this internationally innovative endeavor, are all made possible. Being a section 8 Company, it will not be listed on a stock exchange, however, the board composition, accountability, and transparency norms may be the same as prescribed for listed companies. More than 20 companies, including most of India's leading banks and retail chains, have already registered for ONDC.

Open Network for Digital Commerce (ONDC) is a bold initiative to build an inclusive digital economy of the Country. The possibilities it opens up might hasten the expansion of digital consumption in India and ignite a thriving digital commerce market that is bigger, wider, and more inclusive. The Indian e-commerce economy is expected to expand to become a \$200 billion industry. However, the government must face a number of difficulties and create plans to deal with them. Players that are small to medium-sized have a promising future. More people will spend money on products that reflect their culture and identity, resulting in more alterations to their habits and way of life. As the Indian economy grows, it is inevitable that more of these goods will be consumed. Consequently, the retail e-commerce industry will expand as a result it will bring an end to digital monopolies in the e-commerce industry.

Concerns have been raised concerning the dominance of several platforms given the spectacular growth of e-commerce in India. Small merchants, retailers, and organizations representing numerous traders have regularly questioned the e-commerce duopoly. The Open Network for Digital Commerce (ONDC) initiative, which aims to level the playing field for small enterprises, is now being carried out by the Indian government under the direction of Nandan Nilekani, the founder of Infosys Ltd. In 2021, the project was revealed by the Indian government. By moving digital commerce away from a platform-centric strategy and toward an open network, the government aims to democratize it. The government claims it owes the millions of small business owners a clear explanation of how to take part in the brand-new, rapidly expanding field of internet commerce. ONDC is said to be integrated by 24 firms, including Flipkart-backed Ekart Logistics, rapid hyperlocal commerce start-up Dunzo, and digital payments service Phone pay. Meanwhile, Alibaba and Ant Group have exited Paytm Mall's parent company, Paytm E-commerce Private Limited (PEPL), because the firm's business focus has shifted from traditional physical products e-commerce to ONDC and export. ONDC is initially being implemented in five cities: Delhi NCR, Bengaluru, Bhopal, Shillong, and Coimbatore.

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2. Objective

The primary objective of this paper is to study the approach & thought process behind the development of ONDC. Besides these objectives, to comprehend other core ideas of ONDC is another objective of this paper.

3. Genesis of ONDC

When the COVID-19 pandemic first hit the nation, the Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade (DPIIT), Ministry of Commerce and Industries, launched a large outreach effort to learn more about how it might affect small businesses and the operation of hyperlocal supply chains. Through these interactions, it became clear that there is a big gap between the size of online demand and the local retail ecosystem's capacity to participate. Further studies on the matter underlined the bottlenecks of the existing digital commerce ecosystem in India. Subsequently, consultations were held with multiple ministries as well as industry experts to identify possible solutions to address the bottlenecks in India's digital commerce ecosystem. Taking cognizance of the inherent challenges of the commerce ecosystem, the DPIIT An expert steering committee was established by the Indian government to examine the feasibility of the ONDC idea and its effects. A Project Management Unit (PMU) was established under the auspices of the Quality Council of India (QCI) at the Steering Committee's advice in order to bring the ONDC idea to life. Following the first success, an Advisory Council was established comprising leaders working on population-scale projects in India in addition to the Steering Committee members to expedite implementation. Subsequently QCI was mandated to lead the charge of the implementation of ONDC until the Open Network for Digital Commerce, a Section 8 Company, is established to provide focused attention to nurturing the network.

4. Concept of Open Network

The existing platform-centric approach, in which a transaction between a buyer and a seller requires that both parties be users of the same platform or application, is superseded by Open Network. Alternatively, in an open network, buyers and sellers can transact regardless of the platform or application they use to be publicly visible or accessible online. Any network-enabled application will be able to find and engage in location-aware, local commerce across sectors thanks to an open network based on the open protocol. The Open Network concept was created to alter digital commerce in India, just as the Internet Message Access Protocol (IMAP)/Simple Mail Transfer Protocol (SMTP) is for emails, HTTP is for the World Wide Web, and UPI is for payment systems. The fundamental ideas of decentralization, openness, and increased user usefulness form the foundation of the open network. Based on these ideas, the network will support and promote the rapid adoption of technological stacks and tools such as blockchain, artificial intelligence, machine learning, etc. through innovation and experimentation at each node. It has the potential to transform both B2C and B2B transactions. The open network concept is not restricted to the retail sector and its use cases and benefits can be extended to any digital commerce domains including wholesale, mobility, food delivery, logistics, travel, urban services, etc.

5. Building Blocks of ONDC

5.1 An overview of technology components of ONDC building blocks

The many network components, such as the buyer and seller apps, gateway, registry, and other components, as well as the building blocks, such as adapter interfaces, that may be utilized to create these network components, make up the technological components..

5.1.1 Adaptor Interfaces:

Adaptor interfaces are the open APIs created in accordance with the open-source interoperable specification of the Beckn protocol. These interfaces' documentation is available at www.ondc.org. These APIs will allow sharing of information for the implementation of transactions, allowing all network participants to communicate and integrate via interfaces certified by the ONDC.

5.1.2 Gateway:

Application that ensures search capabilities of all sellers in the network by broadcasting search requests from buyer applications to all seller applications, by criteria such as location, readiness, and other customer preferences. To launch the operations, ONDC plans to provide a Gateway through its technology partners initially. With increased volume of transactions, it is anticipated that multiple gateway providers will emerge with independent service offerings in the network.

5.1.3 Open Registries:

Applications that keeps the corresponding list of participants that take part in ONDC, the catalog of network policies, etc.

5.1.4 Buyer and Seller Edge Applications:

These applications will allow end-users and sellers or service providers to conduct business on the ONDC network. To encourage initial participation, ONDC may roll out reference buyer and seller edge applications directly or via its

technology partners. Open-source reference applications will also be made available for service providers to adopt and build upon in order to join the ONDC network

5.2 An overview of network participants of ONDC building blocks

The network participants will come from a variety of industries, including retail, logistical service providers, dining establishments, and lodging facilities. They may be generally divided into two categories: both the buyer and seller sides. One network participant can act as both the buyer and the seller as part of the network, providing buyers, sellers, and network participants with enhanced options. For instance, a marketplace with retailers can act as both the buyer and the seller in the logistics domain for a digital retail transaction. Large digital commerce platforms, small and medium start-ups, and enterprises making their products available over the network or making it possible for other entities to make their products/services available would all be considered network participants. Participants with varying operational scales and technological proficiency would also be included. Depending on their roles within the network, network participants will be in charge of managing the order life cycle. This includes, but is not limited to, customer/seller onboarding, catalog management, order management, invoicing & reconciliation, warehousing and inventory management, logistics, customer support, returns management, payments, etc.

6. Three Core Attributes of ONDC

ONDC could enable economic growth by helping buyers and sellers overcome the challenges to digital commerce through the following three core attributes: —

6.1 ONDC is interoperable. Network participants work together without being configured to any single platform. That means users can tap into the network through any buyer or seller app for digital commerce.

6.2 ONDC is unbundled. ONDC breaks down complex systems into granular activities or micro services. For example, in an e-commerce transaction, the seller-side, logistics, payments, and buyer-side activities can be handled by different entities.

availability and control over a transaction

6.3 ONDC is decentralised. Data

7. Network and Data Policies of ONDC

7.1 Network Policy

To encourage open, inclusive, and sustainable activities on the network, ONDC will implement a basic and flexible policy structure. In order to do this, ONDC will create the norms and code of conduct for various tasks carried out by the network members, from implementation through run-time, in cooperation with them. As the network develops, these guidelines will be regularly updated and published as Network Policy. Implementation, Registration, Subscription, Transaction, Payment, Data Transmission, and Communication are just a few of the areas that these regulations will cover. In order to improve compliance and transparency, ONDC will make an effort to make these regulations machine-readable and enforceable. Further, ONDC will act as a facilitator of dispute resolution among the participants through fair and transparent practices. Towards this, ONDC will attempt to establish mechanisms adopting from the Online Dispute Resolution (ODR) plan published by NITI Aayog and guidelines on this issued by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) for the financial sector.

7.2 Data Policy

The data policy will work to comply with the emerging Personal Data Protection Bill while adhering to the Information Technology Act, 2000. For safe data exchange, ONDC will work to adopt an adaptable legal, institutional, and technological architecture that is consistent with changing data privacy discourse and policy in India and throughout the world. This will strike a compromise between privacy concerns and prospective data policies..

8. ONDC Beyond the Border

While ONDC is currently being tested in India, the issues it attempts to address are really global in scope. Despite global increases in internet access, cross-border trade and digital commerce remain out of reach for many businesses, particularly small sellers, as well as billions of customers. As the network expands, it has the potential to have a worldwide impact on digital commerce in two ways: by supporting cross-border trade and by speeding and democratizing digital commerce across markets.

For ONDC to transform digital commerce beyond the borders of India, four key enablers should ideally be in place: seamless cross-border payment settlements, stringent grievance redressal systems, a globalised taxonomy, and global cooperation to support digital commerce.

9. Challenges before ONDC

Because ONDC is a new platform, it will need to put in a lot of effort to fulfill the high expectations of its customers and the government. Listed below are some of the challenges before ONDC.

9.1 Technological challenges

The key issue for ONDC is to match the platform's technological viability with the growing volume of transactions and clients. It must compete with some of the world's best applications, such as Amazon, Flipkart, and Uber. ONDC is under increasing pressure to stay up with the latest mobile apps and fulfill client demand. Concerns have been expressed concerning zip code coverage and delivery extensions to meet India's demands. Another challenge that the ONDC network will confront in the future is the growing concern about cyber security and online fraud.

9.2 Operational challenges

ONDC expansion is hampered by UPI, digital linking, and mobile network limits. ONDC is already being integrated with Village Level Entrepreneurs (VLE) and Common Service Center (CSC) Grameen eStores. It is, however, currently plagued by operational concerns. Buyers and sellers must keep trust in the ONDC ambition to reach 100 cities by 2022.

10. Discussion and Significance of the Study

This paper focuses on a theoretical framework of ONDC. Based on the review, it is obvious that ONDC is a crucial for the success and growth of the economy. It is said that the ONDC has the potential to be a game-changer for e-commerce in India, but its success will depend on careful planning and execution. It is recommended that the government work closely with industry stakeholders to address the challenges and ensure that the ONDC is implemented in a way that benefits all participants in the ecosystem. ONDC is effort by government of India to boost uses digital commerce in India about 25% over the next two or three years from the current 8%, and touch maximum sellers in the farthest part of our country. If we compare the pros and cons of ONDC platform it seems to have greater challenges than opportunities at initial phase but later on this network will be boon for local level participants as soon as the participation grows in future.

By providing support for network systems for all facets of e-commerce, the ONDC proposal, which is operated by the government, empowers both sellers and buyers to break away from the marketplace that really is prevalent at the current time and move away from the system that is pervasive at the present time.

The ONDC uses open-source protocols to combat the creation of monopolies in the e-commerce industry. Because they lack the essential technology expertise, the great majority of local retailers are at a disadvantage in a platform-centric e-commerce strategy. They will have access to business methods and resources often used by big e-commerce platforms, which will assist ONDC in fostering fair competition.

The government predicts that by the end of this decade, the gross merchandise volume of India's e-commerce industry will have increased from much more than US\$ 55 billion in 2022 to US\$ 355 billion. This objective appears to be considerably more feasible with the help of ONDC.

Because of platforms like ONDC, India is on the right track for innovative solutions to bridge gaps in the e-commerce industries. Although this goal is lofty, it must be balanced by the method's consideration.

This study sought to advance the body of knowledge in the field of e-commerce by providing academics and researchers with a theoretical grasp of the notion and associated challenges of ONDC. This study will assist academics, researchers, and ONDC users learn more about it.

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